

Problems for Teachers? Views of Members of the Irish Mathematics Teachers' Association on Current Issues in Mathematics Education

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This paper examines two surveys carried out by the Irish Mathematics Teachers' Association (IMTA) in 2022 and 2023. They were designed to elicit members' views on issues identified by the IMTA Council as priorities, and hence to enable the Association to carry out its role of advocacy on behalf of its members. The issues and the survey findings are considered using the lens of recent Irish research on matters affecting curriculum implementation for post-primary Mathematics: time allocated to Mathematics; uptake of the highest level course; possible loss of procedural fluency; and teacher shortage. Teachers' stated concerns mirror these matters closely and reinforce the need for the underlying problems to be addressed.

Keywords: mathematics teacher voice; Irish Mathematics Teachers' Association

Introduction

Mathematics education depends crucially on the mathematics teachers who work with students inside and outside school classrooms. Thus, teachers' views are very important, for example both in identifying areas of mathematics education that are proving difficult or contentious and in contributing to system-level discussions on how problems can be addressed. To facilitate the latter process, bodies that represent teachers have a responsibility to learn their constituents' views and transmit them to appropriate audiences.

The Irish Mathematics Teachers' Association (IMTA) (<https://imta.ie>) is one such body. Founded in 1964 and with 1340 members in February 2023, its roles include supporting post-primary mathematics teachers via various forms of continuing professional development (CPD) and providing them with a voice in advocacy and negotiations about matters of relevance in mathematics education. This paper addresses the advocacy role. Its aim is *to report and discuss IMTA members' views as given in their responses to surveys carried out by the IMTA in 2022 and 2023, viewing them through the lens of current research.*

The following section of the paper offers a literature review. There are two aspects; one provides context and outlines recent curriculum changes, while the other focuses on Irish research that highlights problems affecting curriculum implementation. The rationales and methodology for the two surveys are then described, focusing chiefly on the more recent one. Findings are reported and discussed in the light of the literature, and conclusions are drawn.

Review of Literature

Curriculum Structure and Changes in the Last 20 Years

Post-primary education in Ireland is divided into two cycles, Junior and Senior, each with assessment leading to certification: respectively, the Junior Cycle Profile of Achievement (recently replacing the Junior Certificate) and the Leaving Certificate. Most school subjects are offered at two levels, Higher and Ordinary, but Mathematics has also been provided at Foundation level in both cycles. The Leaving Certificate acts as a gatekeeper to higher education. A student's grade in each subject is converted into "points" (initially in the range 0-100, but see below); the student's six best "points scores" are added, and the total is used to rank-order qualified applicants for over-subscribed third-level courses (Oldham, 2007; O'Meara et al., 2020). Within this general framework, two significant changes in the Mathematics curriculum were introduced in the last twenty years, involving major developments both for curricular intentions and for their implementation by teachers.

The first such change was the initiative known as "Project Maths". This aimed to increase the emphasis on problem solving and real-life applications; also, it set out to alter the dominant classroom culture – which focused overmuch on procedural fluency at the expense of conceptual understanding – by encouraging use of student-centred pedagogies. The "Project Maths" curricula for both Junior and Senior Cycle were phased in over several years from 2008. Adjustments to the style and format of the State examinations mirrored the aims of the initiative, one relevant feature being removal of choice from the examination papers (Berry et al., 2021; Byrne et al., 2021; Oldham, 2007, 2019; Shiel et al., 2020). It should be noted that changes in underlying philosophy and intended classroom practice can be very challenging for teachers, especially if their beliefs about mathematics and teaching clash with the new focus, or if there are practical difficulties. A common difficulty is shortage of time, for instance for content "coverage" using student-centred pedagogies (Johnson et al., 2019).

It was hoped that the changes would promote greater uptake of the Higher level Leaving Certificate course: historically low compared with the case for the other two subjects (English and Irish) taken by almost all Leaving Certificate candidates. To support the new curriculum, the higher education institutions agreed that, from 2012, 25 "bonus points" would be added to the Mathematics points scores of applicants who had achieved a satisfactory grade in Leaving Certificate Higher level Mathematics, irrespective of the subjects they intended to study at third level. Uptake indeed increased markedly, from around 16% in 2011 to over 30% by 2017. This is discussed by Shiel et al. (2020) in the context of a wider exploration of aspects of the "success" (however conceptualised) of Project Maths.

The second significant change was part of wider reform of the post-primary Junior Cycle curriculum. For all subjects, the "specifications" are now framed so as to address generic "key skills" such as being creative, working with others, and communicating; also, to reduce emphasis on a terminal examination, there are "classroom based assessments" (CBAs) which contribute to the Junior Cycle Profile of Achievement. For Mathematics, the revised specification was introduced in 2018, with the main alterations being reduction in the number

of papers in the State examination, abolition of the Foundation level course, and introduction of the CBAs (Byrne et al., 2021). The CBAs involve investigational work: an approach which has been addressed for many years in other jurisdictions (for example in England and Wales), but which has been slow to take root in the Irish system (Oldham, 2019). It is intended that some mathematical concepts and skills would be learnt *through* doing the CBAs, rather than the material being taught and learnt first and then applied; altogether, in fact, the revised specification reflects a focus on problem-based learning. Again, this is challenging for teachers, especially if it is at variance with their beliefs and concerns about mathematics education (Johnson et al., 2019). The COVID pandemic led to changes in implementation of the revised curriculum, so research on the implementation is in its infancy.

Problems in Implementation

Problems caused initially by the radical nature of the Project Maths initiative are now a matter of history (Byrne et al., 2021). However, recent Irish publications identify ongoing issues, notably: the time allocated to Mathematics lessons, together with associated problems of curriculum implementation (with implications for further CPD); the effect of bonus points on students' uptake of the Higher level Leaving Certificate course; overall perceived decrease in procedural fluency; and the shortage of entrants to the teaching profession.

The question of *time* is prominently addressed. A study by Prendergast and O'Meara (2017) noted that, while the average time allocated to Mathematics as a proportion of overall teaching time was broadly in line with that in many OECD countries, the annual total was adversely affected by Ireland's short school year. It follows that, if content "coverage" is to be on a par with that offered elsewhere, teachers will have problems in moving towards the recommended – but time-consuming – student-centred pedagogies. Reports (for example: Berry et al., 2021; IMTA, 2012) consistently reveal that teachers are short of time.

It was noted above that students' *uptake of Higher level Mathematics* in the Leaving Certificate had grown markedly. The driving factor, according to the students themselves, is the award of the *25 bonus points* (O'Meara et al., 2023). However, an unintended outcome reported by teachers is that some students who attempt the Higher level are not suited to it (Berry et al., 2021; O'Meara et al., 2020). This places yet more pressure on teaching time.

A related problem – but one that applies more broadly than to the Higher Leaving Certificate – is that of poor *procedural fluency*, notably in algebra and perhaps reflecting conceptual misunderstanding for key aspects (O'Brien & Ní Ríordáin, 2021; Prendergast & Treacy, 2018). Whether this is a consequence of curriculum change is discussed by Shiel et al. (2020). They report that performance of Ireland's 15-year-old students in PISA (the Programme for International Student Assessment) has mainly stayed almost constant over recent years of testing. However, procedural fluency is not the main focus of PISA tests; a more appropriate measure may be the diagnostic test used by the University of Limerick for first-year students enrolled in science- or technology-based courses. Shiel et al. (2020) note that the decline in test scores over the period 1998-2013 antedates the impact of Project Maths and may have a variety of causes. Whatever the reasons, it is a matter for concern.

The final issue to be mentioned here – one that is fairly new in the Irish context – is the severe *shortage of entrants to the teaching profession* especially in some disciplines, including mathematics (O’Doherty & Harford, 2018). The issue receives media attention, notably when teacher unions hold their annual conferences; it has recently prompted a leading article in the prestigious *Irish Times* newspaper (“Teacher shortages”, 2023, p. 11).

Methodology

The first of the two IMTA surveys described in this paper was carried out in April 2022, to collect feedback from teachers both on *the 2018 Junior Cycle curriculum* and on *their reactions to possible reforms for the Leaving Certificate programme* (due at some still unspecified future date). It also sought information on issues caused by the COVID pandemic, but that aspect is omitted here. The survey was drawn up by IMTA Council members and had two parts, one for the Junior Cycle and one for the Leaving Certificate. Both focused heavily on assessment issues, though the former also mentioned teaching time and student readiness for the Leaving Certificate. Most items were quantitative, chiefly of Likert type (with five responses ranging from *Strongly agree* to *Strongly disagree*); the Leaving Certificate part also asked about preferred options for the some of the issues (the number and timing of examination papers; choice on the papers; and coursework design and marking). For a qualitative element, comments were invited via open-ended items. The two survey parts were set up using Microsoft Forms and the links were emailed to all members (1050 at the time).

The second survey was undertaken in February 2023 to provide further data when the IMTA was invited (at short notice) *to make a submission to the Joint Oireachtas Committee on Education, Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science* on the future of science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) in Irish education. Again, the survey was drawn up by members of the IMTA Council. It reflects Council members’ perceptions of key priorities, and strongly echoes the issues in the literature reviewed above: course and assessment structures, teaching time, bonus points, students’ procedural fluency, and teacher shortage. The style was similar to that of the first survey, with a simple format to encourage responses, and the link to the survey was emailed to all 1340 members.

Data were downloaded into spreadsheets. To relate responses to research on the various issues, coverage here is wide rather than deep. For quantitative items, frequencies (percentages) are reported; for the qualitative aspect, the authors independently studied the comments and then agreed on themes. The main focus is on the – broader – second survey.

Results

For the first survey, there were 362 responses to the first part and 387 to the second. The most striking results for Junior Cycle were the wish to retain Foundation level (only 5.3% agreed or strongly agreed with the statement “The removal of the foundation level exam is a good thing”) and the negative opinions on CBAs (just 9.9% agreeing or strongly agreeing that “CBAs are beneficial to students”). Also, 84.8% disagreed or strongly disagreed that “One exam paper is sufficient for [Higher level] students.” For Senior Cycle reforms, 77.3% of respondents “would need to see more [detailed proposals].” However, reduction to one

examination paper (18.0% agreement) was unpopular, while question choice was heavily endorsed (92.4% agreement). Reactions to coursework at this level were nuanced, but CBA-style work was opposed (93.2%) and only 4.5% agreed with teachers grading their own students. Details are available at <https://imta.ie/junior-cycle-reform-members-survey-2022/> and <https://imta.ie/senior-cycle-reform-members-survey-2022/>.

The second survey was completed by 444 members. An overview of responses to the IMTA Council's list of key priorities is provided in Table 1. With regard to Foundation level and CBAs in the Junior Cycle, and choice on examination papers, the findings reinforce those of the first survey. Among other issues, it can be seen that poor algebraic skills, and the need to shorten the Higher level Leaving Certificate course, attracted much agreement; the idea of a non-calculator element in examinations is less popular; and the items relating to improving teachers' pay and conditions received overall support but drew many neutral responses.

Table 1

Responses to issues identified by IMTA Council as key priorities – percentages (N = 444)

Item	SA	A	N	D	SD
Foundation level must be reintroduced at JC level	54.7	28.2	8.1	8.1	0.9
JC HL course is too long and hard to deliver with schools losing contact time for Maths	48.0	33.3	5.9	9.3	3.6
Algebra skills at JC HL have been eroded. This is influenced by new JC HL assessment	58.2	30.7	5.7	4.8	0.7
A second HL paper must be reintroduced at JC level	54.2	27.7	8.8	7.7	1.6
Numeracy skills are worrying – consideration should be given to having a non-calculator style JC exam	19.8	28.3	18.6	25.1	8.3
Validity of CBAs at JC – consider doing 1 at most	86.3	11.7	1.1	0.7	0.2
Revamp LC HL Bonus Points sliding scale only (H1=25, H2=20, H3=15 etc)	42.2	27.5	9.9	12.2	8.1
There must be an element of Choice on LC papers...	74.5	18.1	3.2	3.4	0.9
LC HL course is too long – some items need to be [cut]	66.7	19.4	5.4	6.5	2.0
Urgent measure to address serious shortage of qualified mathematics teachers – bonus pay, tax incentives, etc	53.3	23.4	15.4	7.0	0.9
Fees for PME/Education [i.e. teacher education] courses with maths element should be paid by State	25.9	27.0	26.8	15.7	4.5
Rental support should be available to STEM teachers ... where accommodation costs are prohibitive	29.8	30.5	25.5	11.0	3.2

Note. SA – Strongly agree; A – Agree; N – Neutral; D – Disagree; SD – Strongly disagree.

JC – Junior Cycle; LC – Leaving Certificate; HL – Higher level.

Possible alternatives to the way in which bonus points might be allocated for Higher level Leaving Certificate, other than by the sliding scale specified above, were explored in a further question. Almost half of the respondents (49.3%) agreed with the sliding scale as

given; however, there was support also for the current system (20.0%), for giving bonus points only for entry to relevant courses (15.1%), and for abolishing them altogether (15.5%).

With regard to teaching time for Mathematics, respondents were asked to indicate how many periods per week were assigned for their classes in each year of the two cycles. Table 2 presents the data for 40-minute and one-hour periods. The variation is striking, and the fact that some teachers meet their First Year classes only twice a week is a matter for concern. Also, asked whether they could teach the Higher level Leaving Certificate course in the time available, a disturbing 61.0% chose the response “To get the course done I have to do extra classes with my students” – that is, meeting them outside the “normal” school timetable.

Table 2

Number of classes per week for each year – percentages

School year	40-minute periods (N = 243)					School year	1-hour periods (N = 201)			
	3	4	5	6	7		2	3	4	5
First year	8.7	52.2	36.7	2.4	0	First year	6.7	80.3	12.1	0.8
Second year	3.2	43.3	50.2	2.5	0.7	Second year	7.1	70.8	21.2	0.9
Third year	1.8	28.4	62.9	5.5	1.5	Third year	0	73.0	24.8	2.2
Fifth year	1.2	2.1	36.6	55.6	4.5	Fifth year	0	12.9	75.4	11.6
Sixth year	0	2.7	25.2	60.8	11.3	Sixth year	0	6.9	72.5	20.6

Note. During Fourth Year (offered in some but not all schools), the major focus is not on examination curricula.

There were 115 responses to an item asking about issues omitted from the list in Table 1. From analysis of the responses, three main themes emerged: *shortage of time*; *assessment issues* (further ideas on the number and structure of papers and question choice; some comments on difficulty level and wordiness of questions; bonus points); and *curricular matters* (return of Foundation level Junior Cycle, the gap between Junior Cycle and Leaving Certificate courses, poor standards, individual topics that could be cut or reintroduced, and negative aspects of the CBAs). Further comments (398) were provided in the context of the “class time” / “periods per week” items. While there was some distinction between responses made with regard to the present courses and those that focused on possible course changes to fit the time allocations, overall they constituted a heartfelt plea for more time.

Discussion

Results are now considered through the lens provided by the Irish research literature described above. There is strong overlap between issues examined through academic research and those identified by practitioners: which is not surprising, as some researchers have specifically worked to obtain teachers’ opinions. Additional aspects addressed in the IMTA surveys – teachers marking their own students’ work for State certification, and the number and timing of State examination papers – refer to issues that apply more generally to (especially) Senior Cycle education, and are not unique to Mathematics.

Issues common to the research and survey findings – time allocated to Mathematics (with implications for the content and processes included in the curriculum), low uptake of

Higher level courses, and the apparent decline (for whatever reasons) in procedural fluency – highlight problems in implementing curriculum change successfully. Such problems are not new; they have affected previous phases of curriculum reform (Byrne et al., 2021; Oldham, 2007, 2019). Thus, claims about insufficient or variable teaching time go back at least to the Leaving Certificate courses of the 1980s. With regard to uptake of the Higher Leaving Certificate, this actually increased from below 12% in the early 1990s to over 18%: the outcome of a curriculum change in which uptake issues had to be balanced against perceived maintenance of standards (Oldham, 2007). Addressing that balance is an ongoing challenge. So is the frosty attitude to CBAs; it seems to reflect that teachers have not bought into the intended focus on problem-based learning, as well as indicating practical difficulties.

Conclusion

The surveys reported here were carried out by the IMTA as part of its advocacy role to ascertain teachers' views on key issues. The rich findings and their alignment with academic research have prompted wider circulation. They give voice to one part of the mathematics teaching community – members of the IMTA – and so probably reflect opinions of specialist teachers rather than those for whom mathematics is not their main subject. Within the IMTA, response rates (percentages in the thirties in each case) are reasonable for email surveys of this type, but outcomes may be skewed towards the views of those who chose to participate.

The fact that reported problems echo those from earlier periods of curriculum change points to their intransigent nature. They relate not just to Mathematics curricula but to the place of mathematics in Irish education, and call for urgent system-level consideration of relative priorities. It is tempting to refer to a four-dimensional challenge: length (of courses when appropriately taught and learnt), breadth (number of topics included), depth (per topic), and time (as a proportion of the overall curriculum) – all with implications for success in terms of pedagogies that can be used and meaningful standards that can be attained. We owe it to our teachers to address the issues.

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